

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA **ITALY**

2025
JUNE 9-13

Airborne LiDAR survey for Monte Cefalone Fault structural analysis

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Abstract — High-resolution airborne LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging) products can enable precise fault scarp morphometry in active tectonic regions. In this work, we performed geomorphometric and structural analyses of the NW-SE-trending Monte Cefalone Fault (MCF), the main segment controlling the Campo Felice Basin, in Italy, using a High-Resolution Digital Elevation Model (HR-DEM) derived from a LiDAR point cloud.

The integrated use of HR-DEM-derived products and 3D processing software, complemented by high-precision field data, allowed the precise extraction of key information regarding tectonic morphostructures. The DEM spatial resolution, along with optimized slope analysis, allowed actual scarp identification and improved the detection of the affected geomorphic markers, enabling a detailed along-strike throw measurement. The MCF exhibits a more than 10 m-high post-Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) scarp characterized by variable depositional and erosional processes responding to the long-term (late-Pleistocene/Holocene) fault activity. Morpho-structural analysis reveals the fault system's geometric complexity, demonstrating that highly detailed data is essential for understanding tectonic evolution. The adopted workflow demonstrates how integrated geomorphometric

techniques can enhance fault scarp detection in complex terrains, advancing regional tectonic mapping.

I. INTRODUCTION

Airborne LiDAR data and derived products may enable high-resolution mapping of fault scarps and geomorphological features, making this approach particularly valuable in densely forested, rugged or inaccessible terrain. A high-resolution DEM elaborated from aerial LiDAR data reveal fault-related structures with high spatial accuracy and detail. Moreover, GIS-based geomorphometric analysis can allow for the quantification of fault scarp geometry and system dynamics. These methods contribute to standardized fault scarp characterization, reducing reliance on field surveys [1,2]. In this work, we integrated LiDAR-based data with geomorphometric analyses to quantify fault throws post-LGM landscape evolution in the area of the Campo Felice Basin tectonic depression (Central Apennines, Italy). We analyzed MCF-related morphology using a LiDAR-derived DEM, from which elevation profiles were extracted to quantify post-LGM throws. Our findings may contribute to paleoseismic reconstructions and enhance the understanding of fault segmentation patterns in this tectonically active region. The

study highlights the necessity of integrating high-resolution remote sensing techniques with conventional field-based geological data to achieve comprehensive structural interpretations.

The study area (Fig. 1) is located in the Abruzzo Region, south of L'Aquila city (Italy), and includes the Campo Felice intramontane depression. The Campo Felice plain lies at 1,400–1,500 m a.s.l. and it is bordered by mountain peaks such as Mt. Cefalone (2,142 m) and Mt. Serralunga (1,909 m). The Campo Felice depression is located on the hanging wall of the SW-dipping Monte Cefalone Fault (MCF), part, together with the Monte Orsello Fault (MOF), of a > 30 km-long segmented fault system called L'Aquila-Ovindoli-Celano with evidence of Holocene activity.

The MCF extends NW-SE along Monte Cefalone's southwestern slope with a cumulative throw of 100–250 m since 0.5 Ma and an average dip of 53° [1,2]. It displays a ~ 5 km-long prominent bedrock fault scarp, interpreted as mostly due to the coseismic exhumation occurring during discrete slip episodes since the demise of the LGM (19-20 cal ka BP). Cosmogenic dating and micro-morphology analyses identify four earthquakes with moment magnitude (Mw) greater than 6 on the MCF over the past 10 ka [1,4].

The Campo Felice Basin is bounded by significant geological structures, including active normal faults and inherited thrust faults of the Italian Central-Southern Apennines. The area belongs to the Lazio-Abruzzo carbonate platform, characterized by a complex geological and structural framework.

Figure 1 - Geographical location of the Campo Felice Basin, in Italy.

II. MATERIALS

A. Airborne Data Acquisition

A flight was carried out over the area under investigation by using an autogyro that was equipped with a LiDAR sensor, including GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) and IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) systems, and a digital RGB camera for digital imagery acquisition. The aim of the flight was to get georeferenced data to be used for topographic and photogrammetric mapping.

B. LiDAR Survey

The sensor used consists of a RIEGL™ miniVUX-1DL laser scanner, optimized for surveying natural areas due to its "downward-looking" configuration. Its wedge-shaped prism provides a $\pm 23^\circ$ field of view at 100,000 pulses/sec. A key feature of this scanner is its ability to digitize different return echoes and process the waveforms in real-time. Although the system can record multiple returns for vegetation penetration, this capability was not utilized in the present study due to the bare cover of the slopes. The instrument generated a high-resolution three-dimensional point cloud, enabling the production of a DEM that was subsequently utilized for geological-structural investigations.

C. Digital Elevation Model

The LiDAR-derived DEM was generated at a 0.3 m spatial resolution (Fig. 2). This level of detail surpassed the resolution of the 1:50,000 Geological Map of Abruzzo Region provided by the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - ISPRA). The model allowed for various terrain analyses, including the evaluation of slope gradients, dip directions towards North, and the identification of geomorphological and tectonic structures along the actual MCF surface. Positional checks conducted on selected Ground Control Points (GCPs), measured by differential GNSS surveys during the airborne data acquisition phases, revealed average altimetric errors in the DEM of, approximately, ± 30 cm.

Figure 2 - DEM spatial extension.

III. METHODS

We employed an integrated approach combining ESRI™ ArcGIS Pro software for geomorphometric analysis and AutoCAD™ software for structural measurements to investigate the MCF. This dual-method workflow enabled precise quantification of fault geometry and post-LGM displacements.

A. Geomorphometric Interpretation and Analysis

The High-Resolution DEM was processed using ESRI™ ArcGIS Pro software and was analyzed in combination with Web Map Service (WMS) layers (e.g., RGB orthophotos, geological boundaries, contour lines) enabling detailed identification of: the surface fault trace; fault slickenside location and dip; related tectonic scarp morphology; footwall erosional surfaces; hanging wall depositional bodies; cross-fault drainage incisions. The identified morphostructural features revealed subtle characteristics indicative of fault activity.

B. Structural Analysis

The removal of vegetation, thanks to the map of “slope” and “aspect”, allowed unambiguous location of the fault slickenside base in the DEM. A series of elevation profiles extracted from the DEM (Fig. 4) served as the basis for fault throw calculations, calculated using the method described in [5], which assumes minimal post-LGM sediment accumulation at the scarp due to the steep slope gradient.

Figure 3 - Fault scarp (MCF). The red arrows at the top image indicate the fault plane along the Monte Cefalone southwestern slope [2].

The fault was characterized in terms of dip direction, dip and slip vector by collecting field data. The parameters of the erosional surface of the footwall, used as LGM geomorphic marker, were extracted from the High-Resolution DEM. Then, the AutoCAD™ software allowed to calculate vertical throws along the fault plane using the following formula as proposed by [5]:

$$T = S / (1 - \tan(\gamma) / \tan(\alpha))$$

where:

- T = vertical offset;
- S = surface displacement;

- γ = dip angle of the erosional surface of the footwall;
- α = dip angle of the fault plane.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Profiles

Only profiles intersecting the exposed fault plane were retained to ensure reliable measurements (Fig. 4). The High-Resolution DEM captured scarp details, even in otherwise inaccessible terrain.

Figure 4 - Black lines represent traces of the profiles utilized for MCF throw analysis. The blue line indicates the MCF scarp base. Cyan symbols indicate the fault plane dip.

B. Dip and Dip Direction Calculation

Dip values computed on the DEM indicate an average fault scarp angle of 52° . The dip angle ranges, from 47° to 59° (Table 1), seems to maintain a quite stable pattern [7] likely modified, locally, by erosion and weathering processes acting throughout time. The along-strike constant dip values suggest coeval exhumation of the scarp. The average computed scarp dip value is lower than the slickensides dip measured in the field and reported on the 1:50,000 geological map (i.e., 58°) due to prolonged erosion that degrades the upper scarp. The slight dip changes detected at morphological bends along the trace can be attributed to lithological variations or erosional processes while remaining inconsistent with fault segmentation. Since the LGM there have been minimal but standard adjustments in fault systems while no major reactivation events have been recorded [5,6]. Overall, the continuous dip values indicate tectonic stability, with little evidence of deformation or secondary faulting since the LGM.

TABLE I. DIP AND DIP DIRECTION MEASUREMENTS ALONG MCF.

Profile Nr. of Fig. 4	Dip (°)	Dip Direction (°)
1	47	201
2	59	200
3	53	196
4	49	200
5	57	201
6	50	193
7	49	210
8	50	194
9	56	206
10	55	203
11	52	208
12	57	195

C. Throw Measurements

The average throws (Fig. 5) resulted equal to 13.01 ± 4.87 m across the analyzed fault segments, indicating post-LGM slip activity. Throw measurements, varying from 5 to 20 meters, reveal fault segmentation due to variable slip across different segments. A segmented fault system exhibits varying throw levels as one of its characteristic features. The outcomes obtained confirm previous investigations by [3], which strengthens the understanding about fault segmentation and its impact on the Campo Felice Basin's geographic development. Analyzing a small segment of the MCF revealed evidence of segmentation according to the results of throw variability. Future studies should explore fault segmentation across broader spatial areas to improve our understanding of regional tectonic dynamics.

Figure 5 - Fault throw variations along the twelve profiles of Fig. 4.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The MCF's 5 km-long fault scarp (Fig. 3) exhibits clear evidence of post-LGM displacement, likely associated with earthquakes of Mw 6.2–6.5 [3,5,6].

The LiDAR-derived DEM was used extensively for the actual fault surface identification and characterization. The MCF exhibits a 13.01 m post-LGM vertical throw ($\sigma = \pm 4.87$ m) and a consistent 52° SW dip angle, as measured from twelve profiles using ESRITM ArcGIS Pro and AutoCADTM software assisted elaboration. This highlights the effectiveness of geomorphometry in regional tectonic assessments, particularly in complex terrains, and further advances tectonic mapping in the area. Future work aims to integrate roughness metrics with slope and curvature analyses to automate fault trace extraction, extending this method to the nearby Monte Orsello Fault (MOF).

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This extended abstract was produced while Andrea Ermini was attending the PhD program in Space Science and Technology at the University of Trento, Cycle XXXIX, with the support of a scholarship financed by the Ministerial Decree no. 118 of 2nd March 2023, based on the NRRP - funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU - Mission 4 - CUP E66E23000110001-

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